

1 Simulation model for IEEE 802.11p physical layer in 2 MATLAB

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6 Abstract

We present the implementation of a simulation model for the IEEE 802.11p physical layer in MATLAB. The implemented simulation obtains Packet Error Rate (PER) versus Signal-to-noise Ratio (SNR) curves with an Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) channel for the different transmission rates allowed by the standard. Additionally, we present the implementation of nine theoretical PER models, presented as curves of PER vs SNR. Its objective is to find the theoretical model that more closely approximates the simulated results considering transmission parameters such as the modulation scheme M and the coding rate r .

7 *Keywords:* PER, IEEE802.11p, MATLAB, OFDM

8 Required Metadata

9 Ancillary data table required for subversion of the codebase.

10 1. Introduction

11 Nowadays, wireless communication systems are present in practically all
12 places; a clear example is 802.11p systems that allow the inter-connectivity
13 of vehicles and their environment. The IEEE 802.11p standard [1] covers
14 the Physical Layer (PHY) and Media Access Control (MAC) sub-layer. It
15 is intended for vehicular applications and modifies certain characteristics of
16 IEEE 802.11 due to the operating environment of vehicle networks, which is
17 a rapidly changing environment.

18 The information unit used in the PHY layer is a bit packet, so the best
19 parameter to measure the reliability of transmissions is the Packet Error Rate

Nr.	Code metadata description	Please fill in this column
C1	Current code version	v1.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://zenodo.org/record/3591987
C3	Code Ocean compute capsule	none
C4	Legal Code License	Creative Commons Zero (CC0)
C5	Code versioning system used	none
C6	Software code languages, tools, and services used	Matlab
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Matlab 2017b or higher
C8	If available Link to developer documentation/manual	none
C9	Support email for questions	diego.reinoso@epn.edu.ec

Table 1: Code metadata (mandatory)

20 (PER), which measures the ratio between erroneous packets and the total
21 number of received packets at reception. A packet is considered to be erroneous
22 when one or more bits that make it up are erroneous [2]. Determining the PER
23 is very important for development of upper layer applications and protocols;
24 therefore, theoretical and simulation models for the PER are required.

25 MATLAB offers the WLAN ToolboxTM [3] for the design, simulation,
26 and analysis of Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) communications. It
27 can simulate the PHY of IEEE 802.11ax/ac/ad/ah and 802.11b/a/g/n/j/p
28 standards. Despite its wide variety of options, this toolbox does not provide
29 an step-by-step implementation of the 802.11p PHY and also implies and
30 extra cost for its use.

31 This article presents in detail the implementation of the IEEE 802.11p
32 PHY in MATLAB and also, nine different theoretical PER models. The scripts
33 generate graphs of PER vs the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) in an Additive
34 White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) channel for the different transmission rates
35 allowed by the standard. The results of the IEEE 802.11p PHY simulation
36 are compared with the theoretical models to determine the model that best
37 fits the PHY simulation.

38 The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a de-
39 tailed explanation of the software architecture. Then, Section 3 presents the

40 simulation results and discussion. Next, Section 4 presents the impact of this
 41 work. Finally, Section 5 includes the conclusions and future work.

42 2. Software Architecture

43 The scripts and functions designed for the PER models comparison with
 44 the simulation of the IEEE 802.11p [1] PHY are implemented in MATLAB
 45 and consist of the following:

- 46 1. The IEEE 802.11p transmitter and receiver with all the blocks involved
- 47 at PHY level.
- 48 2. The AWGN channel.
- 49 3. The theoretical models for the calculation of the PER.
- 50 4. Auxiliary scripts.

51 The different functions and scripts involved in the data processing for
 52 IEEE 802.11p PHY can be found in detail in Figure 1. For the AWGN
 53 channel, a MATLAB function is used. The theoretical models for the PER
 54 calculation are implemented separately in other scripts. Auxiliary scripts are
 55 used to obtain and process the data, in addition to displaying the results.

Figure 1: Structure of the functions and scripts of the IEEE 802.11p PHY layer simulation

56 *2.1. IEEE 802.11p PHY implementation*

57 The PHY layer model will follow the training and reception process de-
 58 scribed in the IEEE 802.11 standard [4] which uses Orthogonal Frequency
 59 Division Multiplexing (OFDM). All the elements of the PHY layer are imple-
 60 mented from the signal processing to the creation and preamble appending,
 61 header formation and bit stuffing.

62 Considering a 10 MHz bandwidth, the eight possible combinations of
 63 coding rates and modulation schemes allowed by the IEEE 802.11 standard
 64 [4] associated with the different speeds for data transmission are implemented
 and shown in Table 2.

Modulation Scheme	Bits Per Modulated Symbol (m)	Coding Rate (r)	Data rate v_i [Mbps]
BPSK	1	1/2	3
BPSK	1	3/4	4.5
QPSK	2	1/2	6
QPSK	2	3/4	9
16QAM	4	1/2	12
16QAM	4	3/4	18
64QAM	6	2/3	24
64QAM	6	3/4	27

Table 2: Configurations allowed by IEEE 802.11p [1] [4]

65
 66 The same scripts can be used for any implementation of the IEEE 802.11
 67 standard which uses OFDM as the transmission technique, giving a greater
 68 scope for future use. The standards that can be used are 802.11a/g/n,
 69 considering that they do not work at the same frequency and that also the
 70 bandwidth is different. For example, for the 802.11g standard the bandwidth
 71 is 20 MHz so the data rate would be the double of the ones shown in Table 2
 72 for the same parameters.

73 *2.1.1. Main Simulation*

74 The `simulation_802_11_p` script is the main script which performs
 75 the following tasks:

- 76 • Setting up transmission parameters such as number of packets, number
 77 of bits per packet and SNR range.
- 78 • Calling on the transmission and reception scripts.

- 79 • Simulating the transmission, sending and reception of packets according
80 to the established parameters.
- 81 • Calculating performance parameters such as Bit Error Rate (BER),
82 PER and number of errors for each configuration.

83 *2.1.2. Transmission*

84 For the implementation of the packet transmission according to the dia-
85 gram presented in Figure 1, the **txOFDM** function is used, which calls for the
86 **Create_SYNC**, **Create_SIGNAL** and **Create_DATA** functions that
87 generate the preamble, header and payload of the packet, respectively.

88 The **Create_SYNC** function creates the short preamble and the long
89 preamble through independent functions. It then appends both to obtain the
90 preamble for the Physical Layer Convergence Protocol (PLCP) Protocol Data
91 Unit (PPDU). The generation of the preamble is given by the IEEE 802.11-
92 2012 standard [1]. The **Create_SIGNAL** function returns the header of
93 the PPDU according to the IEEE 802.11-2012 standard, which is formed by
94 a single OFDM symbol. The **Create_DATA** function returns the DATA
95 field of the PPDU. It generates the SERVICE (16 bits) and Tail (6 bits) fields
96 and the padding bits. It then appends all of them to the PPDU payload
97 according to the IEEE 802.11-2012 standard.

98 The transmission of a randomly generated bit string, grouped in packets
99 of equal size, is simulated. These bits pass through the process described in
100 Figure 2 in order. First, a scrambler shuffles the data with respect to an initial
101 seed. Then, a convolutional encoder adds redundancy bits to implement error
102 correction capabilities. Next, an interleaver permutes the bits inside the
103 packet to avoid burst errors. Then, a modulator assigns complex symbols
104 to groups of bits within the packet depending on the modulation scheme
105 chosen and its corresponding constellation diagram. Next, an OFDM symbol
106 assembler assigns each modulated symbol to its corresponding OFDM symbol
107 sub-carrier. It is followed by the Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) and
108 the appending of the cyclic prefix to reduce multipath effects. Finally, the
109 data is transmitted over the AWGN wireless channel. Reception follows the
110 inverse processes for the recovery of the original bits.

111 *2.1.3. Reception*

112 For the implementation of packet reception according to the diagram
113 presented in Figure 1, the function **rxOFDM** is used, which calls for the

Figure 2: OFDM transmitter block diagram

114 functions **extract_DATA** and **process_DATA** for the extraction of the
 115 DATA field from the packet and its respective processing.

116 The **extract_DATA** function returns the OFDM symbols of the DATA
 117 field that was extracted from the packet according to the IEEE 802.11 standard
 118 [1]. The **process_DATA** function returns a bit payload by performing the
 119 reverse process done in transmission, including demodulation, deinterleaving,
 120 decoding and descrambling according to the IEEE 802.11-2012 standard. This
 121 process is shown in Figure 3. The **extract_OFDM_symbol** function is
 122 also used in **process_DATA** to obtain an array of symbols in the frequency
 123 domain. This function extracts the samples that do not correspond to the
 124 cyclic prefix and redistributes it according to the IEEE 802.11 standard.
 125 Finally, data is extracted from the sub-carriers and the DC sub-carrier.

Figure 3: OFDM receiver block diagram

126 2.2. Theoretical models of PER

127 For each model, a function has been developed that takes the SNR
 128 value, the modulation scheme, the coding rate and the packet length as input
 129 parameters. At the output the value of the PER calculated with the respective
 130 equations of each model is obtained. Other additional parameters that are
 131 necessary for the implementation of the mathematical models are taken from
 132 the specifications of the IEEE 802.11p standard [1].

133 *2.2.1. Mathematical models for BER calculation*

134 Some of the models for the calculation of the PER require BER values
 135 depending on the SNR and the modulation scheme. To obtain these BER
 136 values, three theoretical models are considered and presented below.

137 a) **Theoretical BER model # 1**

138 The first theoretical BER model performs the calculation of the BER
 139 value according to [5]

$$b_e(\gamma) = c_m Q(\sqrt{k_m \gamma}) \quad (1)$$

140 where γ is the SNR, $Q(\cdot)$ is the Q function [6], c_m and k_m are constants
 141 that depend on the modulation scheme defined in the IEEE 802.11
 142 standard. For the different modulation schemes, the BER formulas that
 143 are used are the following

$$\begin{aligned} BPSK : \quad b_e(\gamma) &= Q\left(\sqrt{2\left(\frac{10}{v_t}\right)\gamma}\right), \\ QPSK : \quad b_e(\gamma) &= Q\left(\sqrt{2\left(\frac{10}{v_t}\right)\gamma}\right), \\ 16QAM : \quad b_e(\gamma) &= \frac{3}{4}Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{4}{5}\left(\frac{10}{v_t}\right)\gamma}\right), \\ 64QAM : \quad b_e(\gamma) &= \frac{7}{12}Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{7}\left(\frac{10}{v_t}\right)\gamma}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

144 b) **Theoretical BER model # 2**

145 The second theoretical BER model considers the energy per bit to noise
 146 power spectral density ratio E_b/N_0 value per OFDM symbol is given
 147 by [7]

$$\gamma_s = 0.8 \log_2(M) \frac{AB}{v_t} \gamma = \frac{8m}{v_t [Mbps]} \gamma \quad (3)$$

148 where γ is the SNR value, v_t is the transmission speed in Mbps and m
 149 is the number of bits per symbol depending on the modulation scheme
 150 (BPSK, QPSK, 16QAM, 64QAM). Then, the following approximations

151 of the BER b_e for each type of modulation are obtained

$$\begin{aligned}
 BPSK : \quad & b_e^{BPSK}(\gamma_s) = Q(\sqrt{2\gamma_s}), \\
 QPSK : \quad & b_e^{QPSK}(\gamma_s) = Q(\sqrt{\gamma_s}), \\
 16QAM : \quad & b_e^{16QAM}(\gamma_s) = \frac{3}{4}Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{5}\gamma_s}\right), \\
 64QAM : \quad & b_e^{64QAM}(\gamma_s) = \frac{7}{12}Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{21}\gamma_s}\right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

152 c) **Theoretical model of BER # 3**

153

154 The third model performs the BER calculation with help of MATLAB.
 155 The `berawgn(.)` function of MATLAB is used to calculate this value.
 156 The equations for the different modulation schemes used can be found
 157 in the MATLAB help.

158 *2.2.2. Mathematical models for PER calculation*

159 After the BER models were specified, now the description of each theoret-
 160 ical model is presented in the following.

161 a) **Model 1: Model for vehicular networks by interpolation [8]**

162 This model is a mathematical analytical model for the calculation of
 163 PER, and is given by

$$PER(\gamma, L) = \frac{1 - \tanh(a_R(L) - b_R(L)(\gamma + c))}{2} \tag{5}$$

164 where γ is the SNR in dB, L is the length of the packet in bits, c is an
 165 offset constant, $a_r(L)$ and $b_r(L)$ are parameters obtained as a function
 166 of the modulation scheme and coding rate.

167 b) **Model 2: Model without coding over an AWGN channel using**
 168 **EVT [5]**

169 This model is a mathematical analytical model using Extreme Value
 170 Theory (EVT) for the PER calculation. This model is described from
 171 an SNR value and it is given by

$$PER(\gamma) \approx 1 - \exp\left(-\exp\left(-\frac{\gamma - a_N}{b_N}\right)\right) \tag{6}$$

172 where γ is the SNR, a_N and b_N are constants that depend on the
 173 modulation scheme.

174 c) **Model 3: Model of non-homogeneous errors at PHY layer [2]**

175 This model is a predictive theoretical model of PER that considers the
 176 non-uniformity of errors at the output of the PHY layer due to the
 177 convolutional decoding process. The output bits depend on the input
 178 bits and the constraint length of the code k , for IEEE 802.11p [4] $k=7$.
 The PER value is given by

$$PER(\gamma, L) = 1 - (1 - \lambda(\gamma))^L$$

179 where γ is the SNR and L is the length of the packet in bits.

180 d) **Model 4: Model of PER upper bound for OFDM systems,
 181 with BER equation #1**

182 This model describes how to calculate an upper bound of the PER in
 183 IEEE 802.11p systems. The BER value for this model is calculated
 184 independently with the theoretical model of BER #1 and the PER is
 185 ultimately parameterized with respect to the SNR and the length of
 186 the packet (L) considering convolutional code parameters such as free
 187 distance and free distance path length. The PER value is given by [7]

$$PER \leq 1 - \left(1 - \sum_{d=d_{free}}^{d_{free}+9} a_d P_d^{mod} \right)^L \quad (7)$$

188 where d_{free} is the free distance, a_d is the number of paths of length d ,
 189 and P_d^{mod} is a parameter defined as

$$P_d^{mod} = \begin{cases} \sum_{k=(d+1)/2}^d \binom{d}{k} (b_e^{mod})^k (1 - b_e^{mod})^{d-k} & \text{d odd} \\ \sum_{k=d/2+1}^d \binom{d}{k} (b_e^{mod})^k (1 - b_e^{mod})^{d-k} + \frac{1}{2} \binom{d}{d/2} (b_e^{mod})^{\frac{d}{2}} (1 - b_e^{mod})^{\frac{d}{2}} & \text{d even} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

190 where b_e^{mod} is the BER for the modulation scheme mod .

191 e) **Model 5: Model of PER upper bound for OFDM systems,
 192 with BER model #2**

193 It uses Eq. (7) of model 4, but instead of using the theoretical model
194 of BER #1, the previously described theoretical model of BER #2 is
195 used.

196 **f) Model 6: Model of PER upper bound for OFDM systems,**
197 **with BER model #3**

198 It uses Eq. (7) of model 4, but instead of using the theoretical model of
199 BER #1, the theoretical model of BER #3 is used.

200 **g) Model 7: Model without coding over an AWGN channel, with**
201 **BER model #1.**

202 This model describes a general way for obtaining PER without consider-
203 ing coding schemes on AWGN channels. The BER value for this model
204 is calculated independently with the theoretical model of BER #1 and
205 the PER is given by [5]

$$PER(\gamma) = 1 - (1 - b_e(\gamma))^L, \quad (9)$$

206 where γ represents the SNR, $b_e(\gamma)$ the BER of each modulation scheme
207 used in IEEE 802.11p and (L) the packet size in bits.

208 **h) Model 8: Model without coding on AWGN channel, with BER**
209 **model #2.**

210 It uses Eq. (9) of model 7, but instead of using the theoretical model of
211 BER #1 the theoretical model of BER #2 is used.

212 **i) Model 9: Model without coding on AWGN channel, with BER**
213 **model #3.**

214 It uses Eq. (9) of model 7, but instead of using the theoretical model of
215 BER #1 the theoretical model of BER #3 is used.

216 *2.3. Auxiliary scripts*

217 Auxiliary scripts are designed for the treatment, analysis and presentation
218 of the data obtained with the 802.11p PHY and theoretical PER models.

219 For the evaluation of the PER theoretical models, the function **evalu-**
220 **ate_models** is defined, which chooses the desired theoretical model and
221 executes it for each SNR value of the SNR range entered and saves the results
222 in a PER vector, which is the output parameter.

223 The **PER_Extension** script extends the SNR domain of simulated PER
224 values; this extension is done to be able to graphically represent the PER of
225 each configuration together with the results of the theoretical models.

226 For the collection and consolidation of data resulting from the previous
227 scripts, the function **Data_Consolidation** is created. This function imports
228 the data files generated previously and renames them in a structured way for
229 ease of manipulation, saving all the data in a .mat file.

230 Finally, for the presentation of results, a **Selec_grap** function is created,
231 which shows the results graphically. It is possible to choose between showing
232 only the simulation results, the results of each theoretical model of the
233 PER or the comparison between simulation and theoretical models for each
234 configuration.

235 The simulation of the IEEE 802.11p PHY returns a dataset to graph
236 the results. This simulation takes a total of approximately 40 hours so the
237 previously generated dataset is given. If the user wishes to generate the
238 data again, the **simulation_802_11_p** script can be executed. With the
239 generated dataset, only the **Selec_grap** script is executed to observe the
240 results.

241 3. Simulation results and discussion

242 In this section several figures will present the results obtained with the
243 802.11p PHY simulation and theoretical models. To obtain these results the
244 **Selec_grap** auxiliary script is used. This script generates eight different
245 figures for each configuration allowed by the standard. However, we present
246 only results for a low, medium and high data transmission rate due to length
247 constraints. Additionally, the script obtains the PER figures for both linear
248 and logarithmic scale, but we present in the following the results only in
249 linear scale.

250 Fig. 4 presents the results of the PER vs SNR for BPSK modulation
251 and coding rate 1/2 (3 Mbps transmission rate). It includes each of the
252 nine theoretical models (labeled Model 1, Model 2, ...) in dashed lines. It
253 also includes the results of the 802.11p PHY simulation (labeled Simulation)
254 in black solid line. We can observe that Model 1 obtains the closest PER
255 compared to the 802.11p PHY simulation.

256 Similarly, Fig. 5 presents the results of the PER vs SNR for 16QAM
257 modulation and coding rate 1/2 (12 Mbps transmission rate). In this case,
258 we observe that Model 9 is the closest to the 802.11p PHY simulation.

Figure 4: Comparison of theoretical models with 802.11p PHY simulation for BPSK, $r = 1/2$ (3 Mbps)

259 Fig. 6 presents the results of the PER vs SNR for 64QAM modulation
 260 and coding rate $3/4$ (27 Mbps transmission rate). In this case Model 7 is the
 261 closest to the 802.11p PHY simulation.

262 From the results, we can observe that for each transmission rate the closest
 263 theoretical model is different in each case. Therefore, we can select the closest
 264 theoretical model depending on the transmission rate for best results. Also,
 265 we can introduce SNR offsets to the theoretical models in order to obtain a
 266 model that is the closest for all transmission rates.

267 4. Impact

268 The simulation model of the IEEE 802.11p PHY allows the visualization
 269 of the PER for each of the different modulation schemes with their respective
 270 coding rates. In MATLAB there is no example that computes the PER with

Figure 5: Comparison of theoretical models with 802.11p PHY simulation for 16QAM, $r = 1/2$ (12 Mbps)

271 the four modulations (BPSK, QPSK, 16QAM, 64QAM). Even in the examples
 272 offered by the WLAN toolbox [3] there is none with the characteristics of
 273 the implemented simulation model. Additionally, the simulation of several
 274 theoretical models of the PER is included for comparison with the PHY
 275 simulation.

276 The same implemented scripts can be used for any implementation of
 277 the IEEE 802.11 standard which uses OFDM as the transmission technique,
 278 giving a greater scope for its use in other research topics. The standards
 279 that can be used are 802.11a/g/n, considering that they do not work at the
 280 same frequency and that also the bandwidth is different. For example, for
 281 the 802.11g standard the bandwidth is 20 MHz so the data rate would be the
 282 double of the ones shown in Table 2 for the same parameters.

283 Another objective of this simulation model is to obtain a better approxima-

Figure 6: Comparison of theoretical models with 802.11p PHY simulation for 64QAM, $r = 3/4$ (27 Mbps)

284 tion of the PER to be included in a network simulator such as NS3. Network
 285 simulators are important tools to model the behaviour of a network and they
 286 are widely used for research. However, they usually use very simplified or even
 287 inaccurate models of the PHY. The complete IEEE 802.11p PHY can't be
 288 implemented in NS3 due to complexity constraints. For this reason, obtaining
 289 the theoretical model that best fits the simulated PHY would improve the
 290 results obtained in the network simulator. This work is the first step to bring
 291 more accuracy to the PHY models used in network simulators.

292 The code of the simulation model is provided in full so other researchers
 293 can use it to add other features to the PHY layer such as the effect of
 294 high power amplifiers, more realistic channels, channel estimation, etc. The
 295 same theoretical models can be used to select the one that best fits to any
 296 modification of the PHY.

297 5. Conclusions and future work

298 In this article we presented a simulation model for obtaining the PER in
299 the 802.11p PHY layer with MATLAB. We also presented the implementation
300 of nine theoretical PER models with the aim of analyzing which is the closest
301 model to the 802.11 PHY simulation.

302 According to the theoretical models studied, none of them adapt precisely
303 and accurately to all modulation scheme configurations and coding rates.
304 However, different models can be used by cases, with SNR offsets to obtain
305 the expected results.

306 Compared to the MATLAB WLAN toolbox, our simulation model is
307 open source, free, and allow the access to all scripts and functions used for
308 the 802.11p PHY simulation. Additionally, it gives several theoretical PER
309 models.

310 For future work, we plan to add more realistic channels to the simulation
311 model like a multipath channel with Rayleigh or Rician fading. We also plan
312 to model the effect of the High Power Amplifier (HPA) in the transmitter.

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